

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379505336>

Sustainable financial analysis with special reference to employees cost of selected companies of BSE

Article · February 2024

CITATIONS

0

READS

2

1 author:

Hiren Jani

Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University

5 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Sustainable financial analysis with special reference to employees cost of selected companies of BSE

Hiren Jigarkumar Jani (FIN105)
(Ph.D. Pursuing), GSET, M.Com.
Maharaja Krishnakumarsinhji Bhavnagar University, Bhavnagar
Lecturer,
The K.P.E.S. College, Bhavnagar

Abstract:

The requirement of employees' welfare has been a significant requirement for many years. United Nations have framed the policy of sustainability in which the employees' welfare has been given a major part. Sustainable Development Goals: respectively SDG 3 which deals with good health and wellbeing and SDG 8 which deals with decent work environment. The study focuses on impact of employees cost on firm's sales and enterprise value (market value). The study is conducted on selected companies of BSE pertaining to different sectors. The study provides highlights on importance of employees' welfare and, to find out the possible impact of major financials of selected companies on employees cost. The research design of the study is longitudinal study from 2013-14 to 2022-23. The study is conducted by employing statistical techniques such as regression analysis with 5% level of significance.

Keywords: Employees cost, sales, enterprise value, sustainability, finance.

Introduction: Sustainable Finance

Amidst the recent layoffs by giant corporations especially in countries like USA, UK and also India, many reports have been published regarding the requirement of employees. The Indian scenario has also witnessed the layoffs by many IT firms. The requirement to study the sustainable requirement of keeping the employees in the firm is far more important rather than giving an over importance towards artificial intelligence. Good numbers of managers have reported that sustainability of the firm is highly dependable on maintaining the decent number of employees, and it would be a poor choice to opt for layoffs without giving equal importance to sustainability in long run. The study suggests the importance of employees cost and its impact on sales and enterprise value of selected companies from BSE.

Sustainable Finance is the theme of the study; the term sustainable finance suggests the financial approach towards sustainable paradigm and not wealth or profit maximization. The dimension of the sustainability can be derived from:

E- Environment

S- Social

G- Governance

The current study mainly focuses on the "SOCIAL" aspect, and specially "EMPLOYEES COST". The Employees cost indicates expenses incurred by the organization towards the welfare and wellbeing of the employees.

Employees Cost: An Aspect of Social Parameter of Sustainable Finance:

Employees cost suggests that for the employees' wellbeing and growth, the contribution by the company needs to be given a proper importance. Recent trend of the organization which leads the corporate firms across the world, suggests that lay-offs have taken tolls, the need of an hour

suggests that employees cost can be a major indicator which attributes towards the growth of sales and enterprise value.

Review of Literature:

The importance of employees and requirement of skilled employees has shown a rise in the last decade. The study was conducted in the manufacturing sector of South Africa, taking a sample of more than eight hundred employees, the researchers found negative relation between financial well-being, productivity and absenteeism, and positive relation of financial well-being and productivity. The study contributed by suggesting that managers also give importance of financial well-being of employees and maintaining their personal finance. (Fanus Jansen van Vuren et al., 2018)

The importance of the labour cost cannot be ignored as the economy thrives onto the welfare of the employees. The key concept of labour cost is analyzed with special reference of the earnings as it is the single key factor of labour costs. Labour costs are also analyzed with gender pay gap and minimum wages. (Conn, 2009)

The proper importance has to be given to the financial efficacy so as to balance the financial well-being, satisfaction and remuneration. The study was conducted in South Africa, sample was taken for more than Nine thousand workers. The study was conducted using various statistical tools and the researchers found the strong impact of financial efficacy on satisfaction, financial well-being and remuneration. The study also suggested that proper steps could be taken to address financial issues, as the higher financial well-being will have more positive impact on performance of entity. (Wilmie Vosloo et al., 2014)

Objectives of the study:

The objective of the study is to identify the nature of the selected variables which are sales and enterprise value with enterprise cost.

Conceptual Model:

(figure 1.1- employees cost, sales and enterprise value)

The above figure is the better explanatory depiction of relation between employees cost with sales and enterprise value. The model is tested with 5% of degree of freedom using regression analysis.

List of Selected Companies:

Sr. No.	Company	Industry
1	Astral ltd	Plastic products
2	Oil India ltd	Oil exploration
3	Steel Authority of India Ltd	Steel & Iron products
4	Tata Elexi	IT- Software
5	Torrent Power ltd	Power generation and distribution

(Table 1.1: List of Selected Companies)

Hypotheses of the study:

H0: There is no major impact of sales and enterprise value on employees cost.

H1: There is a major impact of sales and enterprise value on employees cost.

Data Analysis:

Table showing Descriptive Statistics of Each Company:

Descriptive Statistics					
Astral	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees cost	10	23.48	246.6	83.445	21.423
Sales	10	1072.8	4611.6	2122.711	354.507
Enterprise value	10	2707.27	40256.82	16648.09	4420.779
Oil India	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees cost	10	1401.8	1994	1688.505	63.3055
Sales	10	8618.38	21384.91	11787.98	1253.959
Enterprise value	10	14276.28	37099.36	25926.07	2377.55
SAIL	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees cost	10	8781.32	12846.24	9978.517	448.749
Sales	10	39051.88	104447.4	63811.81	7416.617
Enterprise value	10	50533.89	70763.74	59444.02	2223.841
Tata Elexi	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees cost	10	402.96	1597.77	856.199	118.348
Sales	10	1596.93	3144.72	2129.694	199.601
Enterprise value	10	1645.34	54088.69	13551.54	5550.583
Torrent Power	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Employees cost	10	270.33	528.49	444.158	27.9207
Sales	10	8415.55	18836.22	12212.78	907.9114
Enterprise value	10	8491.16	32595.63	20733.32	2438.994

(Table 1.2: Descriptive statistics of the study)

Table Showing Calculations of Pearson Correlation Analysis:

ASTRAL	EMPLOYEES COST	SALES	ENTERPRISE VALUE
EMPLOYEES COST	1		
SALES	0.979	1	
ENTERPRISE VALUE	0.836	0.906	1
OIL INDIA	EMPLOYEES COST	SALES	ENTERPRISE VALUE

EMPLOYEES COST	1		
SALES	0.524	1	
ENTERPRISE VALUE	0.276	0.481	1
SAIL	EMPLOYEES COST	SALES	ENTERPRISE VALUE
EMPLOYEES COST	1		
SALES	0.817	1	
ENTERPRISE VALUE	-0.325	0.089	1
TATA ELEXI	EMPLOYEES COST	SALES	ENTERPRISE VALUE
EMPLOYEES COST	1		
SALES	0.549	1	
ENTERPRISE VALUE	0.808	0.485	1
TORRENT POWER	EMPLOYEES COST	SALES	ENTERPRISE VALUE
EMPLOYEES COST	1		
SALES	0.725	1	
ENTERPRISE VALUE	0.856	0.837	1

(Table 1.3: Pearson Correlation Analysis)

The above table 1.3 suggests that, Astral, Tata Elexi and Torrent Power have positive correlation on employees cost. While Oil India have also positive correlation but it is not quite significant. Whereas SAIL has Positive correlation of sales on employees cost, whereas negative and correlation of enterprise value on employees cost.

Table Showing Calculations of R-Square, Adjusted R-Square and P-Value:

	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	P-Value
Astral	.975	.968	.000
Oil India	.276	.069	.323
SAIL	.826	.776	.002
Tata Elexi	.685	.596	.017
Torrent Power	.733	.657	.010

(Table 1.4: R-Square, Adjusted R-Square and P-Value)

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Sales, Enterprise_Value.
- b. Dependent Variable: Employees_Cost.

The above table suggests that R-Square as well as Adjusted R-Square of the calculated values, have more than significant i.e. 50% above in all major companies have impact on employees cost. Except the Oil India company, all companies shown that null hypothesis is rejected, which indicates that majority of the companies are recorded significant impact of sales and enterprise value on employees cost.

Table Showing Findings of the Study:

	Astral	Oil India	SAIL	Tata Elexi	Torrent Power
Result	Positive	Negative	Positive	Positive	Positive

(Table 1.5: Findings of the Study)

Results & Discussion:

From the data analyzed above, it is proven that majority of the firm have witnessed impact of growth in sales and enterprise value comparing it with the employees cost. The R Value of all selected companies is favouring the decision that, there exists a potential relation between

employees cost and sales and enterprise value. Except the Oil India Company in majority of the companies, the null hypothesis is rejected, as majority of the results favours the significant impact on employees cost. The study is very important as both R-square and Adjusted R-Square have shown very favourable relationship impact on employees cost.

Hence, it is proven that significant impact of employees cost is there in the context of sales and enterprise value. Statistics also support the claim; therefore the strong relationship between these variables is established.

Conclusion:

The sustainability is the major aspect in the world of finance, the main intention behind the study was to analyze the social aspect of sustainability. The study is helpful to establish the connection that, employees cost such as salary, incentives, financial motivations etc... Could not be ignored as it is influenced by the growth in both sales and value of the enterprise. The results suggested that there exists significant impact on employees cost.

References

- Conn, S. (2009). Labour costs. *Economic and Labour Market Review*, 3(2), 47–53.
<https://doi.org/10.1057/elmr.2009.28>.
- Fanus Jansen van Vuren, Prof Jaco Fouché, Jaco Barnard, & Dr Leon de Beer. (2018). MODELLING PERSONAL FINANCIAL WELLBEING ON EMPLOYEE COST IN THE SOUTH AFRICAN MANUFACTURING SECTOR. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 10(1), 80–95.
- Kanchan, M., & Etcfo. (2024, January 2). ‘Cost cutting’ on employees can be a bad idea - A CFO’s calculation. *ETCFO.com*. <https://cfo.economictimes.indiatimes.com/blog/cost-cutting-on-employees-can-be-a-bad-idea-a-cfos-calculation/106393827>
- MoneyControl. (n.d.). Moneycontrol. Retrieved January 22, 2024, from https://www.moneycontrol.com/stocks/company_info/print_main.php
- Wilmie Vosloo, Jaco Fouche, & Jaco Barnard. (2014). The Relationship Between Financial Efficacy, Satisfaction With Remuneration And Personal Financial Well-Being. *International Business & Economics Research Journal*, 13(6), 1455–1470.
<https://doi.org/10.19030/iber.v13i6.8934>